

1 Article

2 Evaluation of the SBAS InSAR service of the 3 European Space Agency's Geohazard Exploitation 4 Platform (GEP)

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27 **Abstract:** The analysis of remote sensing data to assess geohazards is being improved by
28 web-based platforms and collaborative projects such as the Geohazard Exploitation Platform
29 (GEP) of the European Space Agency (ESA). This paper presents the evaluation of a surface
30 velocity map generated by this platform. The map was produced through an unsupervised
31 Multi-temporal InSAR (MTI) analysis applying the Parallel-SBAS (P-SBAS) algorithm to 25
32 ENVISAT satellite images from the South of Spain acquired between 2003 to 2008. This analysis
33 was carried out using a service implemented in the GEP called "SBAS InSAR". Thanks to the map
34 generated by the SBAS InSAR service, we identified processes not documented so far; provided
35 new monitoring data in places affected by known ground instabilities; defined the area affected by
36 these instabilities; and studied a case where GEP could have been able to help in the forecast of a
37 slope movement reactivation. This amply demonstrates the reliability and usefulness of the GEP
38 and shows how web-based platforms may enhance the capacity to identify, monitor and assess
39 hazards associated to geological processes.

40 **Keywords:** DInSAR; GEP; SBAS; landslides; human-induced subsidence; hazard identification

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42 1. Introduction

43 Web-based platforms and collaborative projects are revolutionizing the way to analyze remote
44 sensing data. Moreover, new Earth Observation (EO) missions provide accurate information in time

45 and space, which constitute a significant amount of data waiting to be analyzed. To accomplish this
46 task, web-based processing tools and user networks will take a leading role (see e.g.
47 <https://www.globalexplorer.org/>; [1]). The European Space Agency's Geohazard Exploitation
48 Platform (GEP) (<https://geohazards-tep.eo.esa.int/#/>) is a web-based platform that allow users to
49 perform analysis of satellite data via Internet [2]. This platform hosts several services to identify,
50 monitor and assess hazards associated with active seismicity, vulcanism, subsidence or landslides,
51 among others. The SBAS InSAR service is one of these services that is specialized in producing
52 velocity maps of the Earth surface by applying one specific advanced Differential SAR
53 Interferometry (DInSAR) algorithm. DInSAR was originally applied to analyze the deformation
54 related to earthquakes [3]. In the last decades has proved to be a powerful tool to detect and
55 monitor active processes such as rock dissolution- and human- induced subsidence [4–8],
56 slow-moving slope instabilities [9, 10] or volcano inflation and/or destabilization [11] among others.
57 These slow movements not only can generate damages on buildings or infrastructures [6,12], but
58 also may be precursors of volcanic eruptions [13] or other hazardous fast-moving phenomena such
59 as ground sudden collapses [14,15] or landslides [16,17].

60 The power of DInSAR techniques has being mainly exploited only by specialized research
61 teams or private companies. The cases studied using these techniques were limited to areas where a
62 great number of SAR acquisitions were available, mostly located in Europe, North America and
63 Eastern Asia. GEP and new satellite missions such as Sentinel-1 open a new scenario where
64 researchers and technicians from all around the World would have the possibility to assess hazards
65 in their regions performing their own DInSAR analyses.

66 GEP at present-day is only a beta prototype that is being fine-tuned and its results must be
67 validated by experienced research teams and compared with independent data. In this paper, we
68 present a detailed evaluation of the GEP results in the central sector of Andalusia (South Spain),
69 where we accounted for previous InSAR results related to active landslides and subsidences due to
70 groundwater pumping [18–21]. We compared previous DInSAR displacement rates with velocities
71 obtained by the GEP platform to check them. Moreover, in order to assess the usefulness of this
72 platform, we did not restrict our analysis to areas of previously known deformation, but validate
73 some points where GEP results pointed to active deformation but no active processes have been
74 described up to now. The present work explores the trustworthiness and usefulness of the ESA's
75 platform, by a research team independent to the developers of the SBAS InSAR service,
76 complementing the work of Albano et al. [22] in Mexico City.

77 2. GEP, the G-POD environment and the SBAS InSAR service

78 The Geohazard Exploitation Platform (GEP) is an ESA's web-based platform specially
79 designed to exploit EO data for assessing geohazards. GEP serves as a user-friendly interface to run
80 web tools implemented in the ESA's Grid Processing On Demand (G-POD) environment
81 (<https://gpod.eo.esa.int/>). One of these web tools is the SBAS InSAR service. This service
82 implements the unsupervised P-SBAS algorithm [23,24] that follows the SBAS approach [25], a
83 widely-used technique to carry out multi-temporal DInSAR analysis [26–29]. Inputs of the P-SBAS
84 algorithm are a temporal data set of SAR images of the same region with the same acquisition
85 geometry, the satellite position of all acquisitions and the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the
86 analyzed area [23]. G-POD provides the access to SAR images stored in the ESA's data archives and
87 processes them directly at the server side in the ESA's computing facilities. The users do not need to
88 download and process large amount of data and to acquire and maintain expensive specific
89 processing-software and hardware. De Luca et al. [23] show an overview of the G-POD
90 environment and describes in detail the features and characteristics of the P-SBAS web tool and its
91 implementation in the G-POD environment. Additional information about the platform and its
92 services is available in the following website:
93 <http://terradue.github.io/doc-tep-geohazards/overview/index.html#>

94 At present-day GEP is a beta prototype and its access is restricted to 60 users. They are
95 so-called "Early Adopters" that act as testers of the platform. These users come from companies,

96 academic and research institutions and the Administration. Most of them are from Europe but there
 97 are also users from Chile, Ecuador, Indonesia, Iran, Morocco and USA. Five of them are pilot users
 98 from the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) and the others were included in this
 99 ESA's initiative through the approbation of a research project related to the testing and
 100 development of the platform.
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102 3. Materials and Methods

103 In order to check the reliability, potential and usefulness of the SBAS InSAR service of the GEP,
 104 we selected a well-known area in the central part of Andalusia (South Spain), within the provinces
 105 of Granada and Málaga. With the aid of the GEP service we processed ENVISAT ASAR images of
 106 this area and compared the outputs with previous results. These previous results include InSAR
 107 data produced by our research team as well as previously published information about active
 108 ground instabilities. Additionally, we carry out field explorations to collect evidence of the detected
 109 movements where no previous information about active phenomena existed.

110 3.1. Study area

111 The study area gathers 9130 km² inside a 100 × 100 km Envisat ascending frame of the central
 112 sector of Andalusia (Spain). The rectangle covers the coastal strip of the Malaga and Granada
 113 provinces, from Fuengirola to Salobreña, and also includes a mountain region formed by the
 114 Tejada, Almirajara, Alhama, Chaparral, Guájares, Albuñuelas, Mijas and Los Montes de Malaga
 115 ranges, as well as the high plains of the Llanos de Antequera and the Vega de Granada (Figure 1).
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 118 **Figure 1.** Location of the study area, the main geographical features cited in the text and the areas
 119 referenced in the section 4. The limits of the provinces are defined by dotted lines.

120 The lithology of the main reliefs in the analyzed sector consists of materials from the Internal
 121 Zone of the Betic Cordillera. The eastern mountain ranges are composed of rocks from the

122 Alpujarride Complex, which mainly comprises schists, quartzites, phillites and marbles. The
 123 hillslopes developed in these materials commonly show instability problems and the inventories in
 124 this area draw a high density of landslides associated with these rocks, specially within phillites.
 125 The western ranges exhibit less abrupt landscapes composed of lutites, sandstones, limestones and
 126 conglomerates from the Malaguide Complex. These lithologic formations are less prone to be
 127 affected by mass movements. The high plains of the study area are intra-mountainous basins filled
 128 by Neogene sediments surrounded by low-relief Mesozoic materials from the External Zone of the
 129 Betics. A great variety of mass movements have been described in these high plains [30], as well as
 130 documented human-induced subsidence [19,21,31,32,33].

131 The variability in the climate conditions of this area causes a great heterogeneity in humidity
 132 and the vegetation coverage. Most of the study area shows a semi-arid climate with mean annual
 133 precipitation between 200 and 500 mm and with a scarce vegetation cover. The highest reliefs
 134 (Tejeda, Almirajara and Alhama ranges) show a humid climate with mean annual precipitation up to
 135 1000 mm. These areas are usually covered by Mediterranean forest and shrub but, because of the
 136 terrain characteristics, also bare rock crop out in the highest elevations. The aridity and the scarce
 137 vegetation cover make it an optimal place to apply InSAR techniques.

138 3.2. SAR data and processing methods

139 With the aid of the GEP platform we produced a surface velocity map by processing 25
 140 archived ASAR images of the ENVISAT satellite acquired on ascending orbits from 21 March 2003
 141 to 1 August 2008 (track 459, frame 731). The GEP's SBAS InSAR service allowed to carry out a
 142 Multi-temporal InSAR (MTI) analysis processing 70 interferograms through the Parallel-SBAS
 143 (P-SBAS) algorithm [25] implemented in the ESA GRID-based operational environment [23]. Table 1
 144 shows the values used for the parameters involved in the analysis. Once the surface velocity map
 145 was obtained, unstable points were selected establishing an average line of sight (LOS)
 146 displacement-rate threshold of ± 2 mm/yr. This criterion has been applied in other similar analysis
 147 that used ENVISAT C-band data [6,7,34,35]. Supplementary information on SAR data sets and the
 148 produced surface velocity map is shown in Table 1.

149 The described analysis was performed through the web interface of GEP (Figure 2).
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 153 **Figure 2.** Web interface of the Geohazard Exploitation Platform (GEP)
 154 (<https://geohazards-tep.eo.esa.int/geobrowser/#!>) where advanced DInSAR can be performed. The
 155 three windows of the main website portal and their functions are highlighted.

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Table 1. Main characteristics of the SAR datasets, processing and surface velocity map.

<i>SAR acquisition</i>	
Band / Polarisation	C / VV
Wavelength [cm]	5.6
Incidence angle	23
Revisiting period (days)	35
Orbital track / Frame	459 / 731
Acquisition geometry	Ascending
Pixel size [m] radar geometry	4 x 10
<i>SAR processing</i>	
Number of SAR images	25
Temporal span	03/2003–08/2008 (5.3 yrs)
Number of interferograms	70
Bounding box [Lat, Long, proj.WGS84]	36.49, -4.636 / 36.851, -3.557
Reference point coord [Lat, Long; proj.WGS84]	36.78, -4.1
Processing mode	Multi-Temporal DInSAR Analysis
Max Perpendicular Baseline [m]	400
Max Temporal Baseline [days]	1500
Ground Pixel Dimension [m]	80
Max Allowed Delta-Doppler [Hz]	1000
Max Allowed Doppler Centroid [Hz]	2000
Goldstein Weight	0.5
Coherence threshold	0.7
APS Smoothing Time Window [days]	200
<i>Surface velocity map</i>	
Area [km ²]	9130
No. of measurement points	155474
Density of measurement points [points/km ²]	17
LOS displacement rate [mm/yr]	
Mean	-2
Maximum	+6
Minimum	-17
Standard deviation	1
Cumulative LOS displacement [mm]	
Mean	-4
Maximum	+50
Minimum	-92
Standard deviation	7

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The website provides an user-friendly interface that allows performing the complete DInSAR analysis through the following steps:

1. Selection of the SBAS Service in the *Service window*. After you select the service, the window displays a form to be completed with the parameters of the DInSAR analysis.

- 163 2. Selection the Area Of Interest (AOI) in the *Map window*. By using the tools of the Map
164 window you can draw a rectangle and the system shows you in the *Selection window* the
165 available images coinciding with the chosen AOI.
- 166 3. Selection of the images to include in the analysis. You can drag the images from the
167 *Selection window* to the *Service window*.
- 168 4. Completing the form. You can also select the reference point and include the extension of
169 the analysis using the AOI in the Map window. The system also permits the modification
170 of the input parameters implemented by default.
- 171 5. Running the analysis.

172 The system enabled to develop the entire SBAS-DInSAR processing procedure in an
173 unsupervised way and taking advantage of the computing power of ESA's systems. GEP provided
174 the surface velocity map in less than 24 hours. This map was provided in KMZ format to be
175 visualized in Google Earth and GEP also deliver a TXT file with the coordinates, coherence, velocity
176 and displacement time series of all the measured points.

177 3.3. Interpretation of unstable points detected

178 Although in GEP the SAR image processing needed less than a day, the interpretation of the
179 movements detected in the surface velocity map took several weeks. In our case, we performed a
180 general overview of the results by collecting existing data and studying in detail the points with no
181 previous information.

182 First, we check the InSAR velocity map comparing the detected unstable points of several
183 well-known areas with (1) our own InSAR displacement data obtained through permanent
184 scattered techniques; and (2) InSAR results published in scientific literature. In the latter case, we
185 compare the GEP map with the InSAR data provided for the Granada basin [19,21,31,32],
186 Albuñuelas [31], the Malaga coast [33] and the urban resorts of Marina del Este and Carmenes del
187 Mar in Almuñecar [18,20]. Second, once the GEP map was checked, we carried out a detailed study
188 in the areas with not previous quantitative information about active deformation. We performed a
189 geological and historical analysis in those areas by combining field surveys, modern and historical
190 aerial photographs, digital elevation models, historical documents, and technical and press reports.
191 The available data regarding active processes that we could find in the study area were quite
192 heterogeneous. The information about active landslides was mainly collected from the landslide
193 map of the Granada province [30], a publication about the "Alta Cadena" area (NE of the Malaga
194 province) [36] and the database BDMOVES of the Spanish Geological Survey (IGME).

195 4. Results

196 The InSAR velocity map obtained through the SBAS InSAR service is presented in the Figure 3
197 and its characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The points with coherence level ≥ 0.7 cover the
198 10% of the total area. They are mainly concentrated in bare rock and urban areas. The main surficial
199 processes detected in the study area were human-induced subsidence because of water withdrawal
200 in some points of the Malaga and Granada coast and in the Granada basin. Slope mass movements
201 are the second type of surficial processes identified in the analyzed region. InSAR data derived
202 from GEP agree with several documented cases located along the coast and in some points within
203 the mountain ranges to the South of the Granada province. Alongside with these documented
204 ground instabilities, we also detected new ones and some other surface movements difficult to
205 interpret that will be described in section 4.3.2 (displacements detected in the Zafarraya polje and in
206 the sierras of the Valle de Abdalajís).

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Figure 3. Surface velocity map produced by SBAS InSAR service in the study area.

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4.1. Comparison of GEP results with previous data

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The results derived by the SBAS InSAR service were initially compared with independent InSAR data available for the study area (Table 2). These data were derived using different approaches and techniques than those used in this project to generate InSAR velocity maps. In the following lines, we present several cases to show the correlation of the displacement rate values between the InSAR velocity map produced in GEP and previous InSAR derived data.

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Table 2. Characteristics of the InSAR analysis used to check the GEP results.

<i>Site</i>	<i>Satellite</i>	<i>Temporal span</i>	<i>Technique</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Albuñuelas	ERS1/2	06/1993-12/2000	Small-Area PSI approach	Fernández et al., 2009
Marina del Este	ENVISAT	05/2003-12/2009	Small-Area PSI approach	Notti et al., 2015
Vega de Granada	ENVISAT	05/2003-12/2009	PSIG Cousins analysis	Mateos et al., 2017

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4.1.1. Movements related to slope instabilities

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There are two well-known cases of active landsliding in the eastern sector of the study area: the Albuñuelas and Marina del Este active landslides. The slow-moving landslide that affects the Albuñuelas village was one of the first landslides analyzed using InSAR methods in Spain [30]. The activity of this landslide is evident in the tilting of various buildings within the village (Figure 4). Fernández et al. [31] measured the movements in this place analyzing ERS1/2 images with the Small-Area PSI approach [37]. Their data fit well with the measurements given by GEP although the time span is different (Figure 5). This indicates that the observed displacements detected with images from 1993 to 2000 continue during the period between 2003 and 2008. The movements are currently active as the fresh cracks observed in the buildings and broken gypsum marks on fissures demonstrate (Figure 4A).

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The Marina del Este landslide has been studied recently by Notti et al. [18] processing ENVISAT ASAR images through the PSI approach [38]. These authors provided accurate InSAR

231 measurements in an active landslide that is generating moderate to severe damages in the buildings
 232 of a luxury urban resort on the Granada coast. The activity of this landslide can be also identified in
 233 the GEP's InSAR velocity map (Figure 6).

234 With respect to the measured surface movements, minimum LOS displacement rates of -13
 235 and -17 mm/yr were measured in previous studies in the Albuñuelas and Marina del Este
 236 landslides, respectively [18,31]. The GEP map provides values indicating displacements such as
 237 those above indicated; minimum LOS displacement rates of -8 mm/yr in Albuñuelas and -9 mm/yr
 238 in Marina del Este. In this two cases, the difference between our measures and the previous ones
 239 are related to the spatial resolution of the data. The data of Fernández et al. [31] and Notti et al. [18]
 240 show more point density (points/km²) than the GEP output. In the case of Albuñuelas, the
 241 difference between measurements could be explained by the different time span of the analyzed
 242 images.
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 246 **Figure 4.** Buildings of the Albuñuelas village affected by slight deformations (A) and tilting (B) due
 247 to the activity of a deep-seated landslide on which the village is located.

248 4.1.2. Movements due to groundwater withdrawal

249 The South of Spain is dotted with many cases of aquifer overexploitation that produces surface
 250 subsidence as in the widely known cases of the Vega media of the Segura River and Guadalentin
 251 basin [39,40]. However, the situation due to groundwater withdrawal in the central Betics has
 252 received less attention until the publication of several InSAR analysis [19,21,31,32,33]. One example
 253 described in these publication was used to evaluate the GEP's InSAR velocity map: the subsidence
 254 in the Vega de Granada aquifer [21].

255 The active subsidence described by Mateos et al. [21] is clearly shown by the GEP's velocity
 256 map. The spatial pattern observed in the GEP map agrees with previous data obtained by applying
 257 the PSIG Cousins analysis [41] in the Vega de Granada (Figure 7). Regarding the measured
 258 displacement rates, GEP map point out minimum LOS displacement rates of -13 mm/yr in the Vega
 259 de Granada. These values are coherent with the minimum rates (-10 mm/yr) estimated by Mateos et
 260 al. [21] analyzing the same ENVISAT ASAR images.

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Figure 5. Comparison between the displacement rates measured by Fernandez et al. [30] (A) and the GEP map (B) in the Albuñuelas village. . The boundary of the active landslide is indicated by white dotted lines.

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Figure 6. Comparison between the displacement rates measured by Notti et al. [18] (A) and the GEP map (B) in the Marina del Este resort. The boundary of the active landslide is indicated by white dotted lines.

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Figure 7. Comparison between the displacement rates measured by Mateos et al. [21] (A) and the GEP map (B) in the Vega de Granada.

275 4.2. New active processes detected with GEP

276 4.2.1. Deformation related to slope instabilities

277 Aside from the example of Marina del Este, other urban resorts in the Granada coast have
 278 suffered ground stability problems. Information about these problems is scarce and it has been only
 279 reported in private reports and some local publications [42]. The InSAR velocity map provided by
 280 GEP indicates centimeter-level displacements in Los Angeles, Alfamar and Montes de los
 281 Almendros resorts (Figure 8). We carried out a damage survey to check the impact of these
 282 displacements in the buildings of these resorts and we verified that the detected movements are
 283 producing minor to moderate damages. The Figure 8 shows the most representative damages
 284 observed in the field. The degree of damage is not directly correlated to the magnitude of the
 285 movement, but concerns to the building age and maintenance. The most severely damaged
 286 buildings are the oldest ones because they had to accommodate more deformation (Figure 8C,
 287 D, G and H). With regard to the newest urban developments, the evidence of deformation is clearer
 288 in those buildings that are poorly maintained (e.g. Figure 8K). Even in some well-maintained
 289 buildings, we were able to recognize cracks and fissures repaired and/or recently painted to
 290 improve the appearance of the buildings affected by deformation. In any case, the active
 291 movements in the slopes are evident by the ubiquitous damages in walls and driveways (Figure 8E,
 292 F, I and J) and also the open fractures observed in the bedrock (Figure 8J).

293 Additionally, the GEP's InSAR velocity map helped to identify several active landslides not
294 documented up to date. The best example is an active lateral spreading phenomenon discovered
295 close to the Albuñuelas village. This mass movement covers ~1 km² and mobilizes Tortonian
296 calcarenite rock blocks that run on clays of the Limos Rojos de Albuñuelas Formation creating a
297 basin and range structure at hillside scale (Figure 9). Activity of the lateral spreading is evidenced
298 in the field by open cracks with apertures of meter scale, pipes in the area covered by surficial
299 deposits and fresh fractures with vertical steps (Figure 9E, F and G). This mass movement produces
300 a distinctive landscape not studied up to now. Only the information provided by GEP helped in the
301 recognition of such impressive active landslide.

302 4.2.2. Deformation due to groundwater withdrawal

303 There are many examples of recorded displacements along the Malaga coastal strip. With
304 regard to InSAR studies, Ruiz et al. [33] were the first that identified subsidence in this area by
305 processing ERS SAR images, that cover the period from October 1992 to November 2000, using the
306 Stanford Method for Persistent Scatterers - Multi-Temporal Interferometry (StaMPS-MTI) [43].
307 These authors report active subsidence in Benalmádena, Torremolinos and in the mouth of the
308 Guadalhorce river (Figure 9). The same subsidence pattern is clearly identified in the GEP map and,
309 additionally, we detected other areas with displacements hitherto undocumented within the
310 Guadalhorce valley (Figure 10). They can be probably related to groundwater withdrawal due to
311 the urban development as in the published case of Otura [19]. These places are located in the
312 narrow coastal plains of the Malaga and Granada coast and inland in the Guadalhorce Valley. The
313 extensive urbanization linked to tourism have created new water demands that produced
314 groundwater overexploitation of the coastal and alluvial aquifers and the related subsidence due to
315 aquitard consolidation. The possible subsidence areas located thanks to the GEP map are in the
316 villages of Alhaurín de la Torre, Estación de Cártama, Campanillas, Fuengirola, and Almuñecar
317 (Figures 8A and 10).

318 Most of the movements detected in this area was not reported nor in the scientific literature
319 nor in technical or press reports. Neither those who live in these areas are aware of the surface
320 deformation because they probably are unnoticeable settlements. There is just only one case
321 reported that may be related to the identified movements. Open cracks appeared in the railway
322 tunnel between the Guadalhorce industrial state and the Malaga airport may be associated with the
323 displacements detected just in the area crossed by the railway line (Figure 10).

324 4.3.2. Deformation of unknown nature

325 The GEP's InSAR velocity map shows displacements in an area called the Zafarraya Polje
326 (Figure 11), a karst depression formed by normal and lateral tectonic displacements [44]. The
327 movements in this area were already detected by Ruiz-Armenteros et al. [45] but his interpretation
328 is highly controversial. At first sight, it seems to be related to aquitard compaction due to
329 dewatering of the sediments that infill the karst depression. However, the displacements are also
330 detected where the carbonate bedrock crops out. This fact does not fit well with the hypothesis
331 linked to the dewatering of the surficial deposits. Ruiz-Armenteros et al. [45] argued that the
332 observed displacements may be consequence of the activity of the Zafarraya normal fault.

333 In the study area, there are other areas affected by displacements hitherto unknown. The place
334 where the movements are the clearest but their explanation needs a specific analysis is the ranges of
335 the Valle de Abdalajis. The surface velocity map shows two areas in the top of the hills affected by a
336 surficial slight deformation. In this case it cannot be invoked the effect of groundwater level fall
337 because there are not intensive water pumping and the observed deformation is quite localized. It
338 seems that we are dealing with a type of deep-seated gravitational slope deformation (DSGSD) not
339 previously registered. This slope movement appears to involve large blocks of Jurassic limestone
340 that move over the underlying Triassic materials (evaporites, marls and dolomites) (Figure 12).
341 Similar examples are described in the Betics, Iberian Chain and Pyrenees [46,47,48].

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Figure 8. A) GEP map data of the coast of the Granada province between the Los Cármenes del Mar resort and Salobreña. The urban states with ground instability problems are pointed out. B) Aerial view of the Alfamar resort. C-K) Types of damages observed in the Alfamar and Monte de los Almendros urban states. (1) Horizontal cracks on the top of buildings due to deflections of the slabs due to differential settlements. (2) Diagonal cracks and fissures due to foundation settlements. (3) Deformed walls. (4) Cracks due to deformation of the structure junctions. (5) Curved crack in the asphalt with a small step indicating differential settlement. (6) Open cracks in the bedrock. L) Aerial view of the Monte de los Almendros resort.

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Figure 9. A-B) 3D models of the surroundings of Albuñuelas with the surface velocity provided by GEP. C) Oblique northward aerial view of the horst and graben landscape produced by the active lateral spreading phenomenon (from Google Earth, www.google.com/earth). The yellow marks delimit the area represented in D. D) Oblique northward aerial view of the southern sector of the lateral spreading where the open cracks can be distinguish (from Google Earth, www.google.com/earth). E-G) Field photographs of the cracks with vertical steps of about 1.5 m (E and F) and an example of the piping phenomena identified in the area covered by surficial deposits (G).

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The above explained two cases show how InSAR analysis usually provides information difficult to interpret because different processes can be responsible of the detected motion and the measured signal can contain, apart from ground deformation, contributions from different sources (e.g. atmosphere, DEM, orbits, [49]). For these reasons, further studies need to be carried out in order to unveil the nature of the observed displacements.

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Figure 10. GEP map data of the West of Malaga. The areas with displacements included in the text are located. Note the clear movements detected between the Benalmádena and Torremolinos municipalities not analyzed neither mentioned in press reports so far

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5. Discussion

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5.1. Advantages and limitations of web-based InSAR processing tools

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The results presented in this paper support the reliability of the SBAS InSAR service. The outputs of this service have been checked with data from previous publications or processed by our team, which is independent from the developer-team of GEP platform. Results obtained by different teams never will be equal because the chosen reference points, applied algorithms and parameters. In spite of these limitations, the movements shown in the velocity map provided by GEP, and especially the displacement patterns, are in a good agreement with previous InSAR measurements obtained through different approaches.

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Figure 11. Displacement rate data provided by GEP overlaying a 3D model of the Zafarraya Polje (from Google Earth, www.google.com/earth). Note that the red tones observed in the central sector of the polje are located in the Zafarraya village built on an outcrop of the bedrock.

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Despite the success achieved in the South of Spain, the SBAS InSAR service within the GEP platform has some limitations that must be considered. At present, GEP is a beta-prototype and has to improve some aspect of its interface and processing options. One of the major drawbacks of the GEP platform is the absence of an error-handling tool. Actually, the user does not know why a particular processing ended prematurely. Another important aspect is related to the selection of the reference point. If the point selected by the user is not coherent, the user does not know how the SBAS processing tool selects another reference point. Another less important limitation is related to the control of the coherence level. By default, this level is set to 0.7 and end-users are advised to do not modify it, as this could lead to unexpected results. This value of 0.7 ensures that accuracy and reliability of the measurements will be high. However, sometimes Earth scientists are prone to work with less accurate data, especially if they intent to delineate areas that are in motion regardless the local accuracy. Examples of this are the works of Galve et al. [6], Lu et al. [50] and Chaussard et al. [51], that analyzed karst subsidence, landslides and active tectonics with coherence thresholds of 0.4, 0.6, 0.5, respectively. This is especially true, if the main goal of the analysis is to carry out a preliminary exploration to select points to be visited latter in the field. Therefore, it is needed to address these points better in the web-site and tutorials of GEP, for example advertising that lower coherence levels could be used in particular cases as the ones described or implementing a error-handling tool. The last relevant point to mention is related to the output formats of the SBAS InSAR service. Earth scientists normally handle spatial data by using GIS software such as QGIS and ArcGIS®. At the noticeable exception of the PNG and KMZ files provided, it could be a good idea to implement the most-used vector GIS formats (shapefile, GeoJSON, etc.) for the output files of the service. Moreover, the provided PNG images are scaled and some small areas affected by movements are not displayed. For this reason, it may be also useful to provide raster information at full resolution to identify areas in motion defined by only four or five measure points, as in the case of Marina del Este. Another option could be to manage the outputs directly in the Map window of GEP and to implement a time series tool to see the temporal displacements of a point or a group of points, in order to check immediately the effectiveness of the processing.

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416 **Figure 12.** A) Displacement rate data provided by GEP overlaying an oblique northwestward aerial

417 view of the sierras of the Valle de Abdalajís (from Google Earth, www.google.com/earth). B)

418 Southwestward aerial view of the La Huma mountain where can be recognized a clear fault. The

limestone rock blocks may slide or sink taking advantage of this structure and those associated to it.

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Notwithstanding, a system opened to a wide range of users needs to keep simple but also reliable to prevent malfunctioning and errors. SBAS InSAR service runs a simple unsupervised algorithm that only should be used as a preliminary analysis. Although the service allows modifying the parameters of the analysis, the web-based platform acts as a black box for the end-users, making hard to check the influence of different parameter configurations. On the other hand, it must be taken into account that, thanks to the GEP, the SBAS InSAR service is able to generate, in only one day, displacement maps that cover several hundreds of km². Thus, the service is an excellent tool to obtain preliminary displacement information of a wide region and then delimit areas of interest in which to develop more detailed studies.

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The last observed limitation by our team is not specifically related to the SBAS InSAR service itself but with the availability of SAR images. Currently, the SAR image catalog in the GEP platform is quite heterogeneous in time and space, offering only limited coverage in many regions of the World highly affected by geohazards. This is true in Spain, where the coverage is quite limited, despite being one of the EU countries with higher exposition to geohazards. These limitations are now overcome with the recently implemented web-based services called "TRE ALTAMIRA Fastvel" and "SBAS-InSAR Sentinel-1 TOPS" that perform multi-temporal analysis with Sentinel-1 images.

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5.2. Implications for the hazard analysis community

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The use of web-platforms to perform complex numerical analysis remotely is quickly evolving in many scientific disciplines. Currently, projects as the GEP platform offer the possibility to use complex analysis to a wide range of users, who are focusing more on the interpretation of the results provided by a well-established algorithm (SBAS in our case). In the next decade, we are witnessing an explosion of data availability. Such high volume of data will be impossible to analyze

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441 only by specialized users, i.e. technical users with the required processing knowledge. Therefore,
442 platforms addressed to analyst rather than processing-experts are valuable tools that can expand
443 the analytical capacity of the systems.

444 This is one of the key-objectives of the GEP platform: to allow non-specialized users on
445 satellite image-processing to extract useful knowledge from remote sensing data. The SBAS InSAR
446 service produces InSAR velocity maps that allow analyzing movements and deformations in the
447 Earth surface. Thus far, these analyses were only performed by specialized research teams or
448 companies by using specific complex software and powerful hardware. The results came after a few
449 months and the commercial cost was high (from several thousands to tens of thousands of Euros).
450 Now, the GEP platform offers the possibility to perform a DInSAR multi-temporal analysis of a
451 region in four easy steps: (1) Targeting of the Area Of Interest and a reference point; (2) SAR image
452 selection from GEP catalog; (3) parameters adjustment; and (4) submission of the job to be run in
453 ESA servers. In less than 24 hours the platform provides a InSAR displacement rate map with
454 information about coherence, velocity and displacement time series. This means that, with GEP,
455 geoscientists interested in the understanding of Earth surface movements do not need to learn how
456 to process SAR images or count on expensive software and powerful hardware.

457 The current study shows that the ESA's GEP platform is a powerful tool to identify and
458 monitor ground instabilities at regional scale. Several places affected by subsidence and landslides
459 not documented so far were identified, thus allowing to plan specific field campaigns for gathering
460 additional information about the detected movements. The use of the SAR velocity maps
461 accompanied by field data can facilitate the creation of geohazard inventories, especially those
462 related to man-induced subsidence or slope instabilities. In the case of landslides, by including the
463 naturally unstable slopes into the land planning decision making process, the construction could be
464 limited or even prohibited. For example, if GEP had been operative some decades ago, the great
465 economic losses generated by the landslides of Marina del Este and Los Carmenes del Mar [18,20]
466 could have been avoided. Thus, it is expected that the use of GEP may be crucial for the future
467 urban planning in other hilly and mountain regions of the World.

468 The detection of human-induced subsidence can spot hidden problems of groundwater
469 mismanagement in poorly monitored areas. Most of the cases identified in the Malaga
470 surroundings have not been reported and analyzed so far. There is not available information about
471 the settlements in the detected areas and, if the observed deformation continues, it could produce
472 damages to buildings and infrastructures such as those observed in the railway tunnel of
473 Guadalhorce. On the other hand, the identified surficial movements may indicate overexploitation
474 of the local aquifers and this situation should be managed to avoid future shortage problems in a
475 strategic touristic spot.

476 GEP opens a new period for the hazard identification and monitoring. Soon, it is expected that
477 the ESA's platform can provide information about activity of landslides, subsidence and other
478 phenomena that may damage buildings and infrastructures. Although currently the repository of
479 images of GEP is limited and does not cover the entire surface of the Earth, the performance of the
480 platform will be progressively enhanced with the addition of images from the Sentinel-1 satellite.
481 Sentinel-1 has higher spatial resolution, lesser revisiting times and larger geographical coverage
482 than previous ENVISAT and ERS1/2 ones. This would provide an enormous quantity of
483 information, which will require the involvement, and collaboration of a great number of experts all
484 over the World to interpret the processed data. From the geohazard point of view, the information
485 that is currently registering by Sentinel-1 together with the archived data from old SAR missions,
486 will be the source to produce InSAR velocity maps using GEP. At this point, however, we would
487 like to make a critical comment. The results of GEP are very sensitive information in the policy and
488 legal setting for natural hazards management. For this reason, although the GEP platform is being
489 mainly designed for non-InSAR experts, the use of the platform should be restricted to
490 professionals or researchers specialized in the interpretation of the movements detected in InSAR
491 velocity maps. We consider that the treatment and handling of this information will be crucial to
492 avoid losses without creating controversy or alarm in the society, and this only can be performed by

493 well-trained users and a network of experts who can deal with the uncertainty of the technique and
494 the causes of the detected movements.

495 6. Conclusions

496 The SBAS InSAR service of the ESA's Geohazard Exploitation Platform is a reliable tool to
497 carry out advanced DInSAR analysis. The service provides in less than 24 hours a surface velocity
498 map of a region covering several hundreds of km². These maps can be generated by users not
499 specialized in SAR image-processing but in analyzing and assessing geohazards. This opens a new
500 scenario in the hazard analysis community by enhancing the capacity to identify, monitor and
501 assess hazards associated to geological processes. The recently launched SAR missions such as the
502 Sentinel-1 satellite will provide a large amount of data to be analyzed through GEP. The potential of
503 making new discoveries about active surficial processes, their movement rate and the hazard
504 associated with them has increase significantly with the new available satellite data and the tools
505 implemented in the GEP platform. The platform will help (1) to identify phenomena not yet
506 documented; (2) to monitor known deformations; (3) to delineate precisely the areas affected by the
507 processes that modify the Earth surface; and (4) to forecast future acceleration of the movements or
508 catastrophic ground failures. This paper has presented examples detected using an InSAR velocity
509 map produced by GEP that illustrate all these cases. We (1) identified a lateral spreading not
510 recorded in any landslide inventory or publication; (2) collected time-series in places affected by
511 landslides and subsidence already documented; (3) delimited areas affected by subsidence due to
512 water extraction with a reasonable precision; and (4) detected the deformation in the Marina del
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522 **Author Contributions:** Jorge P. Galve is the main responsible of the study. He generated the surface velocity
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524 main writer of the manuscript. J. Vicente Pérez-Peña and José Miguel Azañón significantly helped in the
525 drafting and edition of the manuscript and contributed in the coordination of the project. J. Vicente
526 Pérez-Peña, Cristina Reyes-Carmona and Antonio Jabaloy carried out with Jorge P. Galve the field survey.
527 Damien Closson, Fabiana Caló, Davide Notti, Gerardo Herrera, Marta Bejar and Oriol Monserrat contributed
528 to the technical aspects of InSAR data treatment, analysis and interpretation and provided previous InSAR
529 data. Patricia Ruano and Rosa M. Mateos, searched information about the impact of the detected surface
530 movements, verified the geological interpretations and revised the manuscript. Philippe Bally managed the
531 relationship between the developer team of GEP and our research team; and provided up-to-date information
532 about the development of the ESA's platform. All authors contributed to the final edition of the manuscript.

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